

Intact protein analysis

The expanding role of proteoforms in health and disease

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EPIC-XS

Rationale behind looking at intact proteins

Many protein forms (**proteoforms**) from a single gene

What is a proteoform?

Canonical
Sequence
(UniProtKB)

Endogenous proteolysis
mRNA splicing
Mutations
SNPs

Site specific features (PTMs):
Govern activity, localization, interactions, half-life

A distinct molecular form of a protein product arising from a single gene

The Consortium for Top-Down Proteomics

Measuring Intact Proteins (Simple Idea!)

Bottom-Up Proteomics (BUP)

Protein identification based on peptide identification (partial sequence coverage)

Top-Down Proteomics (TDP)

Denaturing vs native top-down MS

Denaturing Top-down	Native Top-down
Denaturing separation	Native separation (e.g. SEC, IEX)
Partial organic solution (H ₂ O, ACN, Formic Acid, pH 1-2)	Aqueous solution (H ₂ O, Ammonium Acetate, pH 6-8)
MW of single subunit	MW of protein complex and subunits, non-covalent interactions, stoichiometry and structure
Automated analysis (LC-MS)	Manual injection
Complex mixture	Purified samples
Max. MW ~50 kDa (LC-MS/MS)	Max. MW >1,000 kDa

Native

Denatured

Full MS spectra acquired from intact trastuzumab

Proteoforms are closer to phenotypes

Intact proteoforms

Trypsin digestion

Proteotypic peptides

Bottom-up

Ambiguous result
Upregulation of methylated and phosphorylated peptides
(exact proteoforms unknown)

nature | methods

PERSPECTIVE

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Best practices and benchmarks for intact protein analysis for top-down mass spectrometry

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One gene can give rise to many functionally distinct proteoforms, each of which has a characteristic molecular mass. Top-down mass spectrometry enables the analysis of intact proteins and proteoforms. Here members of the Consortium for Top-Down Proteomics provide a decision tree that guides researchers to robust protocols for mass analysis of intact proteins (antibodies, membrane proteins and others) from mixtures of varying complexity. We also present cross-platform analytical benchmarks using a protein standard sample, to allow users to gauge their proficiency.

Decision tree for intact protein sample clean-up, preparation and analysis

- Proteoform-level knowledge is essential to understand biological function
- Important clinical areas of interest where proteoforms have been identified and linked to disease progression

- Multiple myeloma is a malignancy of plasma cells characterized by a clonal expansion of abnormal B-cells
- B-cells accumulate in the bone marrow and secrete large amounts of monoclonal light chains that can deposit in organs such as kidneys leading to:
 - Light Chain Deposition Disease (LCDD) for aggregates of amorphous nature
 - AL-amyloidosis, where aggregates consist of amyloid fibrils

Amyloid light-chain (AL) amyloidosis

<https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/15718-amyloidosis>

- Currently no possibility to predict the *in vivo* solubility and deposition behavior of a particular LC
- No link between LC abundance and disease severity
- To understand the factors affecting solubility and develop diagnostic tools, LC sequence is essential
 - RNA sequencing of B-cell clones
 - Mass Spectrometry

- MS extensively used for the characterization of recombinant mAbs (BUP with different enzymes)
- For unknown mAbs:
 - Combination of bottom-up proteomics and intact mAb mass profiling
 - Combination of bottom-up and middle-down proteomics on Fab (50 kDa) after sample fractionation
 - Top-down proteomics on LCs extracted from human sera for classifying plasma cell disorders (21T FT-ICR MS)

Limitation of current methods

- Gaps in sequences
- 70% sequence coverage for LC study (TDP)
- No I/L differentiation, S-S assignment

Our objective

Develop a complete *de novo* MS sequencing workflow for patient-derived LC proteoforms

Collaboration A. Buell
(Technical University
of Denmark)

De novo sequencing: step 1 (multiple digestions)

- Enzymatic digestions

- Specific cleavage
- Non-specific cleavage

Trypsin (K, R)
Lys C (K)

Pepsin
Nepenthes fluid

- Sequence assembly

De novo sequencing: step 2 (analysis of intact proteins)

- Sample preparation: **no digestion!**
+/- [reduction, alkylation] of S-S bonds
- LC-MS/MS on Orbitrap Fusion Lumos
Multiple fragmentation techniques
- Data analysis
Xtract (FreeStyle), ProsightLite, 5 ppm

Example for the P15 sample

Candidate seq. 1
 M_{theo} : **23,461.50 Da**

DLQMTQSPST	LSASVGDAVT	LTCRASQSLN	VWLAWYQQKP	GKPPKLLLYE	AS <u>N</u> LESGVPS	RFSGSGSGTE
FTLTLSSLQP	DDFATYYCQQ	YNSYPYTFGQ	GAKLELKRTV	AAPSVFLFPP	SDEQLKSGTA	SVVCLLNIFY
PREAKVQWKV	DNALQSGNSQ	ESVTEQDSKD	STYSLSSTLT	LSKADYEKHK	LYACEVTHQG	LSSPVTKSFN
RGEC						

Candidate seq. 2
 M_{theo} : **23,462.47 Da**

DLQMTQSPST	LSASVGDAVT	LTCRASQSLN	VWLAWYQQKP	GKPPKLLLYE	AS <u>D</u> LESGVPS	RFSGSGSGTE
FTLTLSSLQP	DDFATYYCQQ	YNSYPYTFGQ	GAKLELKRTV	AAPSVFLFPP	SDEQLKSGTA	SVVCLLNIFY
PREAKVQWKV	DNALQSGNSQ	ESVTEQDSKD	STYSLSSTLT	LSKADYEKHK	LYACEVTHQG	LSSPVTKSFN
RGEC						

P15: Intact Mass Analysis

M=23,576.48 Da

Reduction

$\Delta m = -114.93$ Da

$\Delta m = +4.03$ Da \rightarrow 2 disulfide bonds
 $\Delta m = -118.96$ Da \rightarrow cysteinylation (119.00 Da)

M=23,461.55 Da

Match with sequence 1

Sequence 1
+ 2 disulfide bonds
+ 1 cysteinylation

P15: Top-down fragmentation maps

NCE
20%
25%
30%

CID

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L F P P S D E Q L
126 K S G T A S V V C L L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L L
176 S S T L L T L S K A D Y E K H K L L Y A C E V T H Q L G
201 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

nr fragments: 114
Residue cleavage: 46%

EThcD

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L F P P S D E Q L
126 K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L L
176 S S T L L T L S K A D Y E K H K L L Y A C E V T H Q L G
201 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

nr fragments: 253
Residue cleavage: 69%

Reaction time + NCE
1.5 ms + 5%
5 ms + 5%
10 ms + 10%

└ c/z fragment ions
└ b/y fragment ions
└ a/x fragment ions

NCE
10%
12%
15%

HCD

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L F P P S D E Q L
126 K S G T A S V V C L L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L L
176 S S T L L T L S K A D Y E K H K L L Y A C E V T H Q L G
201 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

nr fragments: 99
Residue cleavage: 44%

UVPD

```
N D L Q M T Q S P S T L S A S V G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q S L N V W L A W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E
51 A S N L E S G V P S R F S G S G S G T E F T L T L
76 S S L Q P D D F A T Y Y C Q Q Y N S Y P Y T F G Q
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V F L F P P S D E Q L
126 K S G T A S V V C L L N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
151 D N A L Q S G N S Q E S V T E Q D S K D S T Y S L L
176 S S T L L T L S K A D Y E K H K L L Y A C E V T H Q L G
201 L S S P V T K S F N R G E C C
```

nr fragments: 164
Residue cleavage: 54%

Reaction time
20 ms
25 ms
30 ms

Sequence 1

2 S-S + 1 cysteinylation

Δ mass (Exp. / Theo): 0.95 ppm

nr fragments: 375

Residue cleavage: 85%

┌ c/z fragment ions

└ b/y fragment ions

└ a/x fragment ions

5 ppm fragment mass tolerance

- Analysis of trypsin digest (+/- reduction/alkylation)
 - 100% sequence coverage
 - Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys88, Cys134 – Cys194
 - Cysteinylation on Cys214

z to w ion
EThcD

EThcD to generate z and w ions
 $\Delta w-z_L = -43 \text{ Da}$
 $\Delta w-z_I = -29 \text{ Da}$

Immonium ion
HCD

Small b or y ion containing I or L
 \downarrow HCD (MS3)
 m/z 86
 \downarrow HCD (MS4)
 m/z 69

P15: Ile/Leu differentiation

LLIYEASN**L**ESGVPSR

LLIYEASN**L**ESGVPSR

κ isotype

DIQMTQSPSTLSASVGDAVTITCRASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPGKPPKLLIYEASNLESGVP
SRFSGSGSGTEFTLTISSLQPDDFATYYCQQYNSYPYTFGQGAKLEIKRTVAAPSVFIF
PPSDEQLKSGTASVVCLLNNFYPREAKVQWKVDNALQSGNSQESVTEQDSKDESTYSLSS
TTLTISKADYEKHKLYACEVTHQGLSSPVTKSFNRGEC*

* Cysteinylation

Intact mass analysis

Two proteoforms @:

23,407.35 Da

23,428.39 Da

$\Delta = +170.13$ Da

$\Delta = +149.09$ Da

Reduction

Alkylation

One proteoform @:

23,577.48 Da

A single sequence with modified Cys

De novo sequencing and fragmentation mass analysis

```

N D[L]L[Q]M[T]Q[S]P[S]T[L]S[A]S[V]G[D]R[V]T[L]T[C]R[A] 25
26 S[Q]S[L]S[S]S[L]A[W]Y[Q]Q[K]P[G]K[A]P[K]L[L]L[Y]D 50
51 A[S]S[L]E[T]G[V]P[S]R[F]S[G]S[G]S[G]T[E]F[T]L[S]L 75
76 S[S]L[L]Q[P]D[D]F[A]T[Y]Y[C]Q[H]Y[N]S[Y]S[L]T[F]G[Q] 100
101 G[T]K[V]E[L]K[R]T[V]A[A]P[V]V[F]L[F]P[L]S[D]E[Q]L 125
126 K[S]G[T]A[S]V[V]C[L]L[L]N[N]F[Y]P[R]E[A]K[V]Q[W]K[V] 150
151 D[N]A[L]L[Q]S[G]N[S]Q[E]S[V]T[E]Q[D]S[K]D[S]T[Y]S[L] 175
176 S[S]T[L]L[T]L[S]K[A]D[Y]E[K]H[K]V[Y]A[C]E[V]T[H]Q[G] 200
201 L[L]S[S]P[V]T[K]S[F]N[R]G[E]C*
    
```

Δ mass (Exp. / Theo): -1.03 ppm

nr fragments: 468

Residue cleavage: 86%

Trypsin digest

Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys88 & Cys134 – Cys194
 Cys214*: Cysteinylation or CoenzymeM (CoM)

CoM: adjuvant in chemotherapy

Intact mass analysis

Two proteoforms @:
 23,543.49 Da
 23,776.61 Da

Reduction
Alkylation

Two proteoforms @:
 → 23,713.62 Da
 23,946.81 Da

Two different sequences
modified Cys

Top-down fragmentation map (5A)

```

N L[E]V[L]T[Q]S[P]G[T]L[S]L[S]P G E R[A]T L S C R[A] 25
26 S Q[S]V[S]S S Y L[A]W[Y]Q[Q]K[P]G Q[A]P R[L]L L[Y] 50
51 D[A]S T[R]A[T]G[L]P[D]R[F]S[G]S G S[G]A[D]F[L]L[L]T 75
76 L[S]S[L]E[P]E[D]F[A]M[Y]Y C Q[Q]Y G R[S]P[Y]T[F]G 100
101 P G T[K]V[D]L[K]R[T]V A[A]P[S]V[F]L[L]F[P]P[S]D[E]Q 125
126 L K S G[T]A S V[V]C[L]L[N]N[F]Y[P]R[E]A[K]V[Q]W[K] 150
151 V[D]N A L Q[S]G[N]S[Q]E[S]V[T]E Q[D]S K[D]S[T]Y[S] 175
176 L[S]S[T]L[L]T L[S]K[A]D[Y]E[K]H[K]V[Y]A[C]E[V]T[H]Q 200
201 G[L]L[S]S[P]V[T]K[S]F[N]R G E C*
    
```

Δmass (Exp. / Theo): 0.46 ppm
 Residue cleavage: 83%

Trypsin digest

Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys89 & Cys135 – Cys195
 Cys215*: Cysteinylation

Intact mass analysis

Two proteoforms @:
 23,543.49 Da
 23,776.61 Da

Reduction
 Alkylation

Two proteoforms @:
 23,713.62 Da
 → 23,946.81 Da

Two different sequences
 modified Cys

Top-down fragmentation map (5B)

Δmass (Exp. / Theo): 0.6 ppm
 Residue cleavage: 80%

Trypsin digest

Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys88 & Cys134 – Cys194
 Cys215*: Cysteinylation
 94% identity between 5A and 5B

- Based on the ion-ion reactions described in the 90's by J. Stephenson & S. McLuckey in ion traps
- Principle of Proton Transfer Reaction (PTR)
A multiply charged cation is let to react with a singly charged anion (typically originated from a perfluorinated molecule) to generate a cation with reduced charge state

- Can be used on both MS1 and MS2 level to decongestion spectra and improve S/N
PTCR performed in the ion trap of tribrid mass spectrometers

Example of PTCR analysis

- Localization of an unknown modification on a 44 kDa protein

- Orbitrap Tribrid Eclipse
- PTCR 100 ms, 1E6 reagent target
- PTCR mass range selection: 500 to 1500 m/z
- Mass range: 600-8000 m/z
- Resolution = 120k

Improved sequence coverage with PTCR

- Precise localization of an ADP-ribosylation on Asp29

 b/y fragment
 c/z fragment
 ADP-ribosylation

Omnitrap platform for improved top-down analysis

- A novel segmented linear ion trap for enhanced activation and ion storage
- Arsenal of ion activation techniques: CID, ECD, EID ($E > 10$ eV), photo-dissociation and others...

Q-Exactive HF modified with the Omnitrap platform

- Currently available as a retrofit to the Q-Exactive/Exploris instrument series

Application areas: top-down/bottom-up proteomics, native MS, glycomics...

Q-Exactive HF modified with the Omnitrap platform

- Smooth installation (3 days), performance of the Q-Exactive HF (HeLa digest) kept the same

Application areas: top-down/bottom-up proteomics, native MS, glycomics...

P15: ECD 70 ms – MS² (nanoLC time scale)

P15: ECD (non-reduced) – MS²

a
x
b
y
c
z

Residue cleavage: 37%
Out of the S-S bridges: 88%

a : 18%	x : 15%
b : 7%	y : 16%
c : 23%	z : 24%

Excellent sequence coverage out of the S-S bridges allowing their easy localization
(Cronus software, no data deconvolution)

P15: ECD followed by CID (non-reduced) – MS³

First S-S bond has been cleaved leading to new fragment ions

Residue cleavage: 79%

a : 4%	x : 23%
b : 14%	y : 42%
c : 27%	z : 59%

79% sequence coverage in a single experiment

P15: Intact herceptin 150 kDa (infusion) – MS⁴

- TDP is essential for samples with multiple proteoforms
- Improvements required at all steps of the experiments
- The Omnitrap platform holds great promise for efficient fragmentation of intact proteins (even large ones)
More to come: VUV for S-S bond cleavage followed by CID
- Importance of data analysis, new developments required (*de novo* sequencing from top-down data)
- PI trap for proteoform separation (isoelectric focusing)

PROTEOMICS

Proteoforms as the next proteomics currency

Identifying precise molecular forms of proteins can improve our understanding of function

By Lloyd M. Smith¹ and Neil L. Kelleher²

Proteoforms—the different forms of proteins produced from the genome with a variety of sequence variations, splice isoforms, and myriad posttranslational modifications (1)—are critical elements in all biological systems (see the figure, left). Yang *et al.* (2) recently showed that the functions of proteins produced from splice variants from a given gene—different proteoforms—can be as different as those for proteins encoded by entirely different genes. Li *et al.* (3) showed that splice variants play a central role in modulating complex traits. However, the standard paradigm of proteomic analysis, the “bottom-up” strategy pi-

provides invaluable information on protein expression in complex systems. However, as many different gene products, isoforms, and proteoforms can contain the same peptide, direct information about the proteoforms present is lost (see the figure, bottom). This issue is the proteomic analog of the problem of “phasing” in genomics (5)—determining whether multiple alleles are present on the same segment of DNA. The step of digestion into peptides is essential to the success and robustness of the bottom-up strategy, as well-behaved peptides are more amenable to liquid chromatographic separation and MS analysis than are intact proteins. However, only inferences can be made as to the actual proteoform or proteoforms from which the

Downloaded from <http://s>

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